

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Barx1.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Barx1 as a candidate
9 gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Kim, B.M., Buchner, G., Miletich, I., Sharpe, P.T. and Shivdasani, R.A., 2005. The stomach
12 mesenchymal transcription factor Barx1 specifies gastric epithelial identity through inhibition of transient
13 Wnt signaling. *Developmental cell*, 8(4), pp.611-622.